

A Dutch Translation and Multidimensional Structure of the Adjustment Scales for Early Transition in Schooling

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A successful transition to school entails an adaptation process whereby children must acclimate to their teachers, peers, structured learning activities and classroom rules. This process is critical for ensuring their well-being and lays the foundation for future academic success (Bulotsky-Shearer et al., 2020; Campbell & Stauffenberg, 2008; Mann et al., 2017; Micalizzi et al., 2019; Montroy et al., 2014; Reyes et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2022). Unfortunately, many young children face challenges during their transition to school.

Research further shows that many children from underprivileged families fall behind in reading skills and are less likely to progress to higher forms of education. Reports indicate that, in the Netherlands, between 10-15% of school children experience socio-emotional or behavioral challenges (Stevens et al., 2018). Similar figures are observed in other European nations, with the U.K. showing a rate of 18% (Fledderjohann et al., 2021) and Germany at 10% (Biermann et al., 2020). In the U.S., about 16-20% of children demonstrate significant shortfalls in behavioral school readiness (Ghandour et al., 2021), while in Australia the range is between 15-25% (Gregory et al., 2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated these rates in the Netherlands (Achterberg et al., 2021).

Moreover, adaptation challenges can contribute to other socio-emotional problems that may develop in higher grades, thereby affecting future learning pathways (Cicchetti & Sroufe, 2000; Hattie & Yates, 2014; Huaqing Qi & Kaiser, 2003; McLeod & Kaiser, 2004; Ricciardi et al., 2021; Vandell et al., 2010).

Research has shown that differences in school readiness correlate with variations in school trajectories and subsequent adult outcomes (Gregory et al., 2021; Orri et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2019)

Engagement serves as an indicator of the quality of children's participation in their school environment (Fredricks & McColskey, 2012). Children's disengagement in learning mediates the relationship between the quality of the learning environment and their learning outcomes. Disengagement scores as founded by Bulotsky-Shearer et al. (2008) were negatively associated with mathematics, language, and literacy skills. Socially withdrawn behaviors may influence children's positive engagement within learning situations, fostering skill development across multiple academic domains.

Adaptation to school involves a comprehensive process where children must adjust to teachers, peers, and structured learning activities. This study specifically examines how teachers and schools can approach the adaptation process. For teachers to effectively identify and support children with significant adjustment challenges, it is advantageous to use culturally tailored and context-specific behavioral assessments. Early identification and understanding of these problems are vital and can significantly contribute to school success (Murano et al., 2020; Stormont, 2002).

Observing Adaptation Problems

In response to the need for assessment sensitive to the ecology of the classroom and capable of assessing behavior within learning contexts, the Adjustment Scales for Preschool Intervention were developed (ASPI; Lutz et al., 2002). The ASPI was designed to evaluate children in early childhood programs and developed in collaboration with early childhood educators, parents, and professional staff in the Head Start program. The ASPI was later renamed in the Adjustment Scales for Early Transition in Schooling (ASETS; McDermott et al., 2013, 2014) and is now a U.S. nationally standardized instrument, containing 144 items across 24 distinct classroom contexts. It stands out in its methodology for observing children's behavior, like play, learning tasks, peer interactions and teacher engagement in different situational contexts.

What distinguishes ASETS is its focus on context-specific behavior, allowing for a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of classroom dynamics. Initial ASPI studies identified five behavior dimensions: Aggressive, Oppositional, Hyperactive/Attention Seeking, Low Energy, and Withdrawn Behavior (Fantuzzo et al., 2007), collectively referred to as "Phenotype". Subsequent analyses by McDermott et al. (2013) refined these into four behavioral factors, where Aggressive and Oppositional were not distinguished as separate factors, which resulted in Aggressive/Oppositional, Low Energy,

Withdrawal, and Hyperactive/Attention Seeking. Three classroom contexts founded were referred to as “Situtype”: Relationship with the Teacher, Peer Relationships, and Structured Learning.

Theoretical Framework

The ASETS framework emphasizes the critical role of classroom relationships and engagement. Its theoretical basis aligns with the transactional model of development (MacKenzie et al., 2009; Sameroff, 2010). This model posits that classroom behavior is a dynamic process shaped by continuous interactions with the environment, emphasizing the bidirectional influence between a child and their surroundings. In terms of behavioral school readiness, the model suggests that school adaptation is influenced by reciprocal relationships within the school environment, including factors such as school resources, teaching quality, and overall school climate (Dockett & Perry, 2002). Consequently, school adaptation is viewed as a multifaceted construct, profoundly impacted by student-teacher and peer relationships (Jerome et al., 2009; Skalická et al., 2015; Weiss et al., 2022). This underscores the need to consider the broader picture when evaluating children's readiness for structured learning. Research findings feature that positive student-teacher relationships significantly influence children's educational outcomes and behavioral adaptation in a beneficial way (Huaqing Qi & Kaiser, 2003; Pianta et al., 2007). These relationships are particularly beneficial for children facing behavioral challenges or with lower academic skills (Cadima et al., 2015; Hamre & Pianta, 2001). Moreover, ASETS highlights the importance of peer relationships in shaping classroom social dynamics. Children's interactions with their classmates directly influence their social status and behaviors, ranging from aggression, withdrawal, or peer rejection. The classroom environment, including the emotional climate, profoundly impacts these relationships, especially for children who are anxious or withdrawn. Such children often struggle with withdrawal, increasing their risk of social isolation (Arbeau et al., 2010; Rimm-Kaufman & Kagan, 2005; Stormont, 2002).

Present Study

We utilized a Dutch translation and adaptation of the U.S. ASETS. The main research question focuses on identifying the latent factors on the behavioral (phenotype) and context (situtype) dimensions. Additionally, we aim to assess how effectively the instrument distinguishes between children with adaptation problems and those who are not.

The Dutch sample comprises children from regular schools, without selection based on socioeconomic disadvantages or other issues. This sample

reflects the demographic composition of children in typical kindergarten within elementary schools. It significantly differs from the Head Start sample, which includes a higher proportion of children from families facing poverty, social challenges, and single-parent households. Additionally, the Dutch sample likely includes fewer children from diverse ethnic backgrounds.

Given these substantial differences in sample composition, we anticipate identifying different factors. We hypothesize that children in the Dutch sample, having been exposed to fewer adverse conditions and thus experiencing a more normative early childhood, exhibit fewer relational difficulties and possess greater competence in communication with teachers and peers.

Method

Participants

The research included data from 323 kindergarten students attending regular elementary schools, provided by 81 teachers from 30 schools located in urban areas of the Netherlands, including Amsterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht. The kindergarten students were in the second year of kindergarten (in the Netherlands kindergarten is integrated in the first two classes of elementary school), with an average age of 5 years and 8 months ($M = 5.7$ years, $SD = 2.2$ months).

Procedure

To ensure a representative sample, we designed the study to appropriately include children experiencing adaptation problems in kindergarten. Therefore, we asked teachers to select two children from their classrooms for whom they had an explanatory/special meeting or peer consultation separate from the regular school meetings or child review agenda. This meeting must have occurred within a few weeks prior to the survey, and could involve an observation by the school assistant, a collegial or peer consultation, or external (psychological) help or advice.

With a Dutch average class size of 25 pupils this approach was considered optimal for including children from the group of 10-15% of students who have socio-emotional problems (Stevens et al., 2018). Given that kindergarten teachers regard behavior and school adaptation as one of the most important issues, it is evident that many children with behavioral and/or socio-emotional challenges naturally fall into this category and are thus included in the sample.

Teachers were also asked to randomly select two students each who had not been part of these special meetings, i.e. representing the remaining 85-90%

for whom regular student review sessions are sufficient or not necessary (Stevens et al., 2018). We named the first group “Consulted”, and the second “Not Consulted”, referring to the extra consultation of the first group.

The decision to utilize two distinct groups is motivated by the objective to evaluate the instrument's ability to discriminate between children identified in the consulted category, and those without concerns regarding adaptation problems.

In the sample 188 children (58.2%) were reported as “Consulted” by the teachers, while 135 children (41.8%) were classified as “Not Consulted”. Despite instructions for equal gender observation, the sample showed an imbalance in the “Consulted” group, with 56.9% male and 43.1% female participants. In the “Not Consulted” subcategory, 45.2% is male and 54.8% female. Both groups have a mean age of 5.8 years (“Consulted” $SD = .67$, “Not Consulted” $SD = .75$). Of the participating teachers 92% were female and 8% male, with a mean age of 37.9 years ($SD = 11.5$) and working experience of 12.1 years on average ($SD = 9.1$).

The research spanned four academic years, from 2018/2019 to 2021/2022, and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Amsterdam. The study was directed under the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union, therefore, only the teachers themselves had the key (code) to their scores and, as a result, data processing was fully anonymous. Before the start of data collection, all parents/caregivers of participating children provided active consent.

Measures

Translation and Adaptation

The translation and adaptation process were carried out in two steps, starting with a professional translation and subsequent back-translation of the ASETS by a professional translation bureau, *UvA Talen*, at the Academic Language Center of the University of Amsterdam. This aimed to ensure the reliability and contextual accuracy of the item descriptions in the Dutch version. To ensure a good fit with the Dutch educational culture, a panel of kindergarten teachers conducted a critical review of the translated items. This was crucial for adapting the questionnaire to the nuances of common Dutch school terminology, and bridging possible cultural differences between the U.S. and Dutch educational settings.

Secondly, in collaboration with our research team, these educators, with at least five years of experience, provided critical feedback, leading to the refinement of the questionnaire. This process involved editing and consolidating some of the original ASETS items to eliminate redundancies, and the inclusion of new items to address specific areas they identified as lacking in the initial version.

These supplementary questions were tailored to capture distinct elements of Dutch kindergarten practices, such as student behavior during circle time activities.

Analysis

Items depicting positive or neutral behaviors, which do not contribute to the assessment of problematic behaviors, were omitted from the analysis. As a result of this and the review and modification process, the Dutch adaptation of the ASETS has a total of 106 items, systematically organized across 24 contexts, exclusively focusing on the identification of problematic behaviors. This analysis proceeded in seven phases.

First, the completion of a data review and the removal of observations with incomplete data.

Second, we created a smoothed tetrachoric matrix for the phenotype. There were concerns about the potential instability or inaccuracies that can arise when dichotomous item data are treated as continuous (e.g., Bernstein & Teng, 1989; Mooijaart, 1983). To address this, Waller and Reise (2010) proposed using iterative factoring of a smoothed tetrachoric matrix. For this method we used Statistical Analysis Software (SAS), version 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc.). The approach involves a two-stage maximum-likelihood estimation as described by Olsson (1979).

Third, an EFA was conducted (using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 28), with various rotations (varimax, equamax, and promax), following Snook and Gorsuch (1989) recommendation for handling item sets of 50 or more. The ideal structural solution was identified based on several criteria: It should approximate a simple structure, as per Yates (1987), and have at least four significant items per factor (with loadings $\geq .40$ indicating significance). Further, it should produce internally consistent factors (with a reliability coefficient of at least .70), and be theoretically sensible, providing parsimonious and compatible coverage of the data in line with existing research, as suggested by Fabrigar et al. (1999). From the existing theoretical model, in which the latent constructs were already specified, the EFA starts with trying to replicate the 4-model U.S. structure (McDermott et al., 2013), with all factor loadings $\geq .40$. By anticipating this number and nature of the factors, we expected to obtain and use this as a guide for selecting the items.

Fourth, the situtype factor structure was explored using an EFA, utilizing the 24 situational contexts. Fifth, a Pearson correlation was conducted between the phenotype and the situtypes. Sixth, we explored the sensitivity of the measure with a discriminant analysis. Seventh, we conducted a Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis.

Results

Phenotype Analysis

Due to the large number of 106 items, it was not feasible to create a nonsingular matrix. The smoothed matrix was then analyzed using the Minimum Average Partialling (MAP) method proposed by Velicer (1976) to determine the maximum number of components to retain. At this point the sample was randomly split for further analysis.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure indicated sampling adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .79$, which was above the acceptable limit of $.5$. After oblique rotation, items with factor loadings $< .40$ and items with multiple factor loadings were removed, resulting in a final set of 81 items (see Table 1). Items loading on the components 1 and 3 indicated factors related to externalizing problem behavior, Hyperactive/Attention Seeking and Aggression/Oppositional behavior. The second component represented internalizing problem behavior, Withdrawal/Low Energy. The reliabilities measured with Cronbach's α were between $.86$ and $.92$ (see Table 1).

Sitotype Analysis

We utilized the 24 contexts of the ASETS to explore the sitotype factors. The promax rotation with a smoothed polychoric matrix demonstrated optimal performance for the $K=3$ equamax configuration, particularly in terms of reducing the number of multiple loaders and maximizing the number of items with salient loadings (see Table 2).

The α coefficient for the first factor was $.84$. Example contexts included "Controlling sudden outbursts" (Context 24), "Respecting other's belongings" (Context 16) and, "reacting to correction" (Context 10). These contexts depict situations necessitating interpersonal discipline, and responses to disciplinary actions. We refer to this factor as Contexts Requiring Discipline (Indiscipline).

The α coefficient for the second factor was $.85$. Example contexts included "Sitting during teacher-directed activities" (Context 15), "Answering questions" (Context 3) and, "Paying attention in the classroom" (Context 11). These contexts focused on learning situations that require attention to the teacher or instructions. We refer to this factor as Problems in Contexts of Teaching and Learning.

The α coefficient for the second factor was $.80$. with example contexts including "Getting involved in classroom activities" (Context 13), "Talking with teacher" (Context 5), and "General manner with teacher" (Context 7). These contexts describe general situations where children are expected to demonstrate

engagement with activities, materials, and the people around them. This factor is termed Contexts Requiring Engagement (Disengagement).

Correlation and Reliability

Using a Pearson correlation the subscales revealed, as expected, only low correlations for Withdrawal/Low energy with Hyperactive/Attention Seeking (.04, not significant) and Aggression/Oppositional (.13*), as shown in Table 3. Additionally, a low correlation was found between Discipline and Withdrawal/Low energy/ (.25).

There are strong associations between pronounced Discipline issues and Hyperactive/Attention Seeking behavior (.82), as well as significant relations with aggression and oppositional behavior (.82). This also includes notable hyperactivity and difficulties in situations that require paying attention to the teacher (.79). Additionally, hyperactive behavior strongly correlates with challenges in maintaining attention to the teacher (.75). Reliability coefficients range from $\alpha = .84$ to $\alpha = .92$.

Discriminant Analysis and Receiver Operator Characteristic

Table 4 presents the discriminant and structure coefficients for the three behavioral dimensions. Hyperactive/Attention Seeking, and Withdrawal/Low Energy contribute most to the prediction of group membership as different and, hence, complementary components. The canonical correlation between the groups is .53, which corresponds to an effect size of .28, i.e., a medium correlation. The classification results of the predicted group membership indicate that 141 out of 188 children (75.0%) of the “Consulted” group were correctly classified. For the “Not Consulted” group, 113 out of 135 (83.7%) were correctly classified.

The curve in Figure 1 showed a good overall model quality with measures all $> .5$ and similar curves for all three phenotypes. Values were good for Withdrawal/Low Energy in the upper bound of the curve (.79), followed by Hyperactive/Attention Seeking (.76) and Aggression/Oppositional (.73). The area under the curve (AUC) showed the overall ability of the ASETS to discriminate between the “Consulted” and “Not Consulted” groups. The measures for the area under the curve were .76 for Withdrawal/Low Energy, .74 for Hyperactive/Attention Seeking, and .71 for Aggression/Oppositional.

Discussion

The objective of this study was to evaluate the multidimensional structure of a Dutch translation and adaptation of the U.S. ASETS within a regular kindergarten

setting. The research builds upon prior studies (e.g., Meisels & Shonkoff, 2000a; Xie & Li, 2018), and in particular on the socio-emotional and behavioral ASPI and ASETS measures by Lutz et al. (2002), McDermott et al. (2013; 2014), and Hamerslag et al. (2018).

ASETS in the United States and the Netherlands demonstrates the ability to distinguish between phenotypes and situational types. ASETS facilitates a differentiated analysis of behavior, taking into account both behavior traits and classroom contexts for educators and school counselors. This approach is crucial as it provides a nuanced understanding of how various contexts impact student behavior in everyday classroom settings. It offers insights into the socio-emotional and behavioral challenges children may face in adapting to the school environment, specifically identifying with whom (peers, teachers), when (during specific activities), and with what (materials) these challenges occur.

The Dutch phenotype factors, similar to those in the US, were identified as aggressive/oppositional, withdrawal/low energy, and hyperactive/attention-seeking. However, in the Dutch sample, we did not observe a distinction between low energy and withdrawal as separate factors. This discrepancy may be due to the close relationship between low energy and withdrawal behaviors, making them more challenging to differentiate in the smaller Dutch sample.

This study revealed different situational factors: contexts requiring disciplined behavior, teaching and learning, and engagement. The original U.S. ASETS consists of three situational types, respectively describing problems in contexts involving peers, teachers, and structured learning. In contrast, the Dutch data reveal situational types involving indiscipline and disengagement, which correspond with types discovered exclusively in the U.S. Head Start program (Bulotsky-Shearer et al., 2024). The third Dutch situtype is essentially identical to its namesake in the U.S. ASETS standardization study (McDermott et al., 2014).

We would like to highlight three limitations inherent in our research. First, we could not establish a confirmative analysis for the factor structure due to the many items and in comparison, the number of observations. Two, as mentioned before, in the Dutch sample we did not observe a distinction between low energy and withdrawal as two separate factors. Three, it should be noted that the sample mainly consisted of female kindergarten teachers, which might the generalizability and applicability of the study. However, this unequal gender distribution in our sample reflects the general workforce of teachers in kindergartens of which the majority is predominately female (CBS, Statline, 2022).

This study of the translation and adaptation of the ASETS in the Netherlands provided preliminary evidence for its multidimensional structure and yielded encouraging results.

The translation effectively assesses Dutch schooling situations that are differentially associated with the risk of phenotypic problem behaviors. The varying associations between specific situations and phenotypes highlighted the importance of identifying latent profiles in specific Dutch early schooling contexts as a future research target.

While the discriminant analysis showed that 75.0% of children for whom teachers had concerns and held additional meetings were correctly classified, and the ROC curve acknowledged a good distinction between those groups, further research is needed to deepen our understanding. Future research could examine how kindergarten teachers and parents perceive the Dutch adaptation of the ASETS. Holding meetings to present, interpret, and share observation results can offer valuable insights into behavioral issues and guide teachers and parents in providing emotional support. By taking into account external factors such as socio-economic status (SES) (e.g., (Wei et al., 2021), kindergartens can develop context-based strategies to support families of children experiencing transitional challenges (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

In conclusion, the ASETS framework teaches us that, as educators, we should not solely rely on the phenotypic characteristics of children but should assess whether their behavior is context-dependent (Mischel, 2004), because behavior is far more dynamic than often assumed. For example, engagement is not a fixed attribute of the child, but influenced by contextual factors. If engagement is understood as emerging in the interaction between the child and the environment, it is expected that it will change as the context changes, and the child's dynamic states change (Fredricks & McColskey, 2012). It can be improved by adapting the environment to the child (Skinner et al., 2022). To foster engagement, the school environment can offer ample opportunities for children to interact with their peers, teachers, educational materials, and various activities (Ritoša et al., 2020).

Like engagement, indiscipline is also not a fixed attribute but influenced by situational contexts, however, in young children it also is related to self-discipline, referring to self-regulating skills (Cadima et al., 2015; Montroy et al., 2014). In a kindergarten context discipline is related to learning and play activities often with problems regarding student-teacher and peer relationships (Weiss et al., 2022). In a kindergarten context, indiscipline problem behavior has been found to interfere with peer and teacher relationships, and is associated with higher ratings of peer play disruption and emotional lability (Bulotsky-Shearer et al., 2020).

For children adapting to school with socio-emotional and/or behavioral issues, the Dutch adaptation of the ASETS offers valuable insights for teachers. The instrument reveals that behavior we observe is an expression of latent behavioral traits that emerge in specific situational contexts. As a result, it encourages us to avoid hastily labeling children and instead to observe their

classroom behavior more thoroughly and carefully. With enhanced knowledge and insights into the underlying adaptation challenges students face in the school environment, and a deeper understanding of how to influence behavior, it may become an essential tool for teachers.

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Table 1*Dimensional Structure and Properties of the Phenotype ASETS after Oblique Rotation*

Item description ^a	Pattern Loadings ^b			% Prevalence	Communality	Item/total r ^c
	1	2	3			
<i>Component 1: Hyperactive/Attention Seeking ($\alpha = .92$)</i>						
Talks freely with teacher	.87	-.23	.03	33.13	.86	.66
Answers questions before thinking	.85	-.20	-.05	27.55	.75	.61
Rushes about shouting madly	.82	.23	-.03	3.41	.67	.44
Sometimes seeks disapproval	.81	-.14	-.02	17.03	.68	.58
Makes sudden inappropriate noises	.81	.18	-.13	9.29	.59	.50
Is often the cause of trouble in line	.78	-.03	.18	18.58	.78	.70
Involuntary movements	.77	.18	-.16	2.79	.50	.36
Refuses to take turns	.76	-.07	.13	7.74	.70	.56
Talks, gazes around, plays (not attending)	.75	-.10	.13	29.72	.70	.62
Charges into new tasks without thinking	.74	-.06	-.14	21.36	.48	.50
Experiments with unusual sitting positions	.73	.15	-.03	11.46	.52	.51
Doesn't stay seated when he/she should	.70	.15	.04	13.31	.52	.50
Causes disturbance when not chosen	.70	.00	.20	5.88	.66	.51
Disrupts games by fooling around	.70	.04	.26	17.03	.73	.65
Moves quickly between activities	.69	.20	.00	16.10	.50	.48
Clowns around, plays silly tricks	.68	.05	.09	16.10	.52	.53
Bothers others during teacher directed time	.67	.08	.27	14.55	.70	.61
Physically aggressive means	.66	.02	.30	16.41	.72	.63
Seeks help when not needed	.65	-.07	-.07	14.55	.40	.40
Does things in front of you	.64	.02	.31	17.96	.70	.64
Improves when corrected but not for long	.64	.07	-.02	28.48	.40	.46
Makes sudden aimless movements	.64	.32	-.16	6.50	.40	.35
Talks through teacher instruction	.63	-.14	.11	10.53	.50	.44
Without warning throws objects, etc	.59	.28	.16	4.02	.54	.36
Overly rough with other children in games	.59	.03	.33	9.91	.63	.55
Starts fight and rough play	.56	.13	.38	10.22	.69	.54
Welcomes you loudly	.55	-.32	.04	13.31	.44	.39

Insists on sitting next to teacher	.54	-.08	.19	6.19	.44	.38
Wants teacher interest but holds back	.45	-.37	.13	35.60	.58	.43
Asks for jobs but often does not perform well	.43	.00	.09	9.60	.23	.28
<i>Component 2: Withdrawal/Low energy ($\alpha = .88$)</i>						
Too lacking in energy to be troublesome	-.23	.87	.10	3.10	.86	.55
Sluggish, apathetic in games	-.08	.85	-.25	5.88	.75	.55
Cannot work up the energy for something new	.18	.81	.04	2.48	.70	.48
Is too timid to join in during free time	-.21	.81	-.16	4.64	.73	.53
Appears to live in a dream world	.31	.77	-.37	15.17	.60	.49
Too lethargic to ask for help	-.16	.77	.18	4.02	.63	.49
Allow others to push ahead in line	-.07	.77	-.29	6.81	.63	.47
Freezes up and doesn't answer questions	-.01	.75	.18	13.93	.64	.53
Distant, makes no relationship with teacher	-.12	.75	.35	10.22	.76	.54
Listless, seems unmotivated	.26	.73	-.08	8.05	.55	.49
Lacks interest, just sits	.27	.73	.07	12.38	.62	.51
Ignores all other students	.08	.72	.07	1.55	.55	.35
Sometimes wanders off by self	.34	.72	-.14	15.17	.55	.48
Won't get involved with games	.01	.71	.15	6.19	.55	.42
Does not stand up for self	-.07	.71	-.28	14.86	.55	.44
Likes the challenge of something difficult	.17	.69	.08	24.77	.52	.48
Usually plays by self during free play	.37	.69	-.13	6.81	.51	.41
Seldom gets involved in any activities	.08	.68	.16	5.57	.53	.41
Appears too withdrawn for jobs	.22	.67	-.16	4.64	.44	.37
Afraid to budge during teacher directed time	.06	.65	.13	0.93	.47	.24
Does not offer with jobs	.06	.63	.07	32.82	.42	.42
Needs encouragement to join in games	.06	.63	-.01	18.58	.39	.45
Uses devices to gain teacher attention	-.03	.61	-.25	14.24	.40	.36
Aloof, seldom says anything to teacher	-.38	.60	.12	5.26	.53	.37
Needs teacher assistance in free play	.00	.59	.10	13.62	.37	.42
Afraid to try with hands	-.08	.58	-.10	8.98	.34	.36
Has one companion only	.22	.51	-.04	7.74	.34	.29
Waits for teacher to greet first	-.09	.43	.25	27.55	.27	.32
Not shy but rarely answer questions	-.13	.43	.06	13.00	.22	.26

Component 3:

Aggression/Oppositional ($\alpha = .86$)

Much too talkative with teacher	-.38	.38	.93	1.86	.95	.37
Tries to dominate	.11	-.28	.85	18.27	.82	.61
Tries to cheat in games	.12	-.16	.81	6.19	.75	.55
Unkind to smaller or weaker children	.03	-.05	.77	5.26	.60	.43
Deliberately destroys others belongings	.33	-.07	.70	6.81	.81	.58
Loses temper if can't get own way	.27	-.06	.67	21.98	.70	.58
Attacks other children if provoked	.31	-.05	.66	10.53	.72	.55
Responds with an angry look	.01	.24	.65	3.41	.53	.37
Takes others belongings without permission	.36	-.03	.64	8.05	.75	.57
Does not greet even after you greet	-.03	.31	.63	9.29	.48	.57
Answer with threats when corrected	.37	-.03	.62	9.91	.73	.58
Snatches objects away from other students	.22	.16	.62	2.48	.62	.36
Wants to dominate during free play	.35	-.33	.58	22.60	.71	.54
Refuses to share toys or other materials	.17	.30	.58	4.95	.60	.44
Repeats what people say	.05	.08	.58	3.72	.39	.39
Tells on others to gain teachers favor	-.25	-.09	.57	7.12	.30	.31
Unprovoked attacks on children	.32	.26	.56	1.55	.70	.37
Tell tall tales about self or family	.14	.00	.56	10.22	.40	.41
Shy, difficult to get to speak to teacher	-.28	.18	.49	13.93	.25	.20
Sometimes in an unfriendly mood with teacher	.31	-.21	.49	9.29	.50	.42
Won't attempt new task if difficulty	.07	.34	.48	12.38	.43	.39
Overly friendly with teacher	-.11	-.26	.47	5.88	.20	.23

Note. ^aItem content is abbreviated for convenient presentation. ^b Pattern loadings $\geq .40$. ^citem/total $r > .20$

Table 2

Context Structure of the Adjustment Scales for Early Transition in Schooling after Oblique Rotation

Context ^a	Pattern loadings ^b			N items
	Discipline	Teaching and Learning	Engagement	
24 Controlling sudden outbursts	.99	-.28	.25	7
16 Respecting belongings	.88	-.08	.08	4
21 Getting along with agemates	.78	.12	.03	6
10 Reacting to correction	.67	-.18	-.06	3
20 Behaving standing in line	.65	.38	-.08	3
22 Handling conflicts children	.65	-.01	.06	5
18 Free play/individual choice	.59	.25	.25	7
06 Valuing teachers's attention	.59	.07	-.28	4
15 Teacher-directed activities	.25	.78	-.22	6
3 Answering questions	-.03	.76	.23	3
11 Paying attention in classroom	.06	.68	.23	4
2 Helping (teacher) with jobs	-.11	.67	.30	4
1 Greeting teacher	-.23	.66	.36	5
23 Exhibiting unusual habits	.38	.63	-.19	5
12 Coping new learning tasks	.27	.40	.24	4
13 Involve classroom activities	-.01	.01	.93	3
5 Talking with teacher	-.20	.02	.92	5
7 General manner with teacher	.11	.13	.56	6
14 Working with hands (artwork)	.33	.20	.47	5
9 Telling the truth	.38	-.01	.45	1
19 Having companions	.14	.33	.43	4

Note. ^a Contexts are abbreviated for convenient presentation. ^b Pattern loadings $\geq .40$, $n = 323$.

Table 3*Correlation and Reliability of Pheno and Situtype Subscales*

Scale	Correlations						Reliability	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	<i>n</i>	α
1 Hyperactive/Attention	1						30	.92
2 Withdrawal/Low energy	.04	1					29	.87
3 Aggression/Oppositional	.56**	.13*	1				22	.86
4 Discipline	.82**	.25**	.82**	1			33	.84
5 Teaching and Learning	.79**	.56**	.61**	.75**	1		38	.85
6 Engagement	.47**	.69**	.58**	.61**	.75**	1	23	.80

Note. $N = 323$; * = significant at .05, ** = significant at .01 (both 2-tailed).

Table 4*Outcomes of Hierarchical Canonical Discriminant Analysis*

Variables	Discriminant	Structure	Mean scores	
	coefficients	coefficients	Consulted	Not
	F1	F1		Consulted
Hyperactive/Attention seeking	.69	.67	.40	-.55
Withdrawal/Low energy	.72	.64	.41	-.58
Aggression/Oppositional	.14	.51	.08	-.11
Eigenvalue	.40			
Canonical correlation	.53			
Wilks' lambda	.72			
Centroids			.53	-.74

Note: n = 323

Fig 1. Receiver Operator Characteristic for ASETS

